

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

PROCEEDINGS OF THE CONFERENCE

January 15, 2026
UWED
Tashkent, Uzbekistan

University of World Economy and Diplomacy

SAMEIR-2026

International Scientific and Practical Conference

**SYSTEM ANALYSIS
AND MODELING IN ECONOMY
AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS**

The conference is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

PROCEEDINGS

(Conference Proceedings)

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International Scientific and Practical Conference – SAMEIR-2026

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

The University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED) hosted the International Scientific and Practical Conference “System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations (SAMEIR-2026)” on January 15, 2026, in Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

The **main goal** of the conference was to bring together researchers, scholars, policy makers, and experts to discuss current scientific and practical issues related to system analysis and modeling of socio-economic and international processes. Particular emphasis was placed on the application of quantitative, mathematical, and computational methods, as well as on the development of interdisciplinary approaches to the analysis of economic dynamics, international relations, and global challenges.

Key Themes of the Conference:

- **System Analysis and Economic Modeling:** mathematical and econometric models in the world economy, analysis of structural changes, and forecasting of macroeconomic and financial indicator.
- **International Relations and World Politics:** quantitative methods for analyzing international processes, modeling of conflicts and cooperation, geopolitical forecasting, and risk assessment.
- **Mathematical and Computer Modeling:** methods of applied and computational mathematics, simulation and stochastic modeling, optimization and control of complex socio-economic systems.
- **Artificial Intelligence and Big Data:** applications of machine learning, artificial intelligence, and big data analytics in economic and international studies.
- **Sustainable Development and Global Security:** economic, environmental, and energy aspects of sustainable development, system approaches to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and issues of information and digital security.

The event was conducted in a **hybrid format** with participation in **English, Russian, and Uzbek**. The conference provided a high-level platform for **scientific exchange, networking, and policy dialogue**.

The authors are solely responsible for the content and accuracy of their articles

Dedicated to the 75th Anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

The International Scientific and Practical Conference “*System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations*” is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of **Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov**, an outstanding scientist, educator, and founder of a recognized scientific school in the fields of system analysis, mathematical and stochastic modeling.

Professor Rasulov’s academic career spans more than five decades and is inseparably connected with the development of applied mathematics, computational methods, and their practical implementation in economic and socio-economic research. His fundamental contributions to the theory and application of Monte Carlo methods, numerical solutions of linear and nonlinear boundary value problems, and stochastic modeling have gained wide recognition both in Uzbekistan and internationally.

A special place in Professor Rasulov’s professional life belongs to the **University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED)**. Since the founding of the University, he has played a decisive role in shaping its scientific and academic profile. As Head of Department, Dean of Faculty, Vice-Rector for Research, and Professor, he consistently promoted a multidisciplinary approach, integrating mathematical modeling, system analysis, and quantitative methods into the study of economics, international relations, and diplomacy. This approach has become one of the distinctive features of UWED’s academic tradition.

Professor Rasulov is not only a prominent researcher, but also an exceptional mentor. Under his supervision, numerous PhD and Doctoral dissertations have been successfully defended. Many of his former students currently hold leading academic and administrative positions, continuing and developing the scientific traditions established by their mentor. The permanent scientific seminar initiated by Professor Rasulov has become an essential institutional platform at UWED, where dissertation research in mathematical modeling and system analysis is regularly presented, discussed, and refined, contributing to the formation of a rigorous and open academic environment.

Professor Rasulov’s extensive international collaborations with research centers and universities in the United States, Japan, Europe, and Asia have significantly strengthened UWED’s global academic presence. His active participation in international research

projects, conferences, editorial boards of leading scientific journals, and grant programs has contributed to the integration of national scientific research into the global academic community.

The present conference brings together researchers from different countries and disciplines, reflecting the breadth of scientific interests inspired by Professor Rasulov's work. The papers included in this volume address contemporary problems of system analysis, mathematical modeling, and their applications in economics and international relations, continuing the scholarly dialogue initiated and supported by Professor Rasulov over many years.

This volume is not only a collection of scientific papers, but also a tribute to Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov's lifelong dedication to science, education, and the development of future generations of scholars. The Organizing Committee expresses its deep respect and sincere gratitude to Professor Rasulov for his invaluable contribution to academic science and wishes him good health, continued creative inspiration, and further success in his scholarly endeavors.

Mathematical models in the process of water resources distribution in main canals of irrigation systems taking into account boundary conditions

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Keywords: effective water management, ntermittent water delivery, agricultural water systems, recursive optimization technique, system regulation theories, finite-variable optimization methods, oscillatory phenomena, computational modeling

Abstract: The article discusses mathematical modeling for optimizing water distribution in primary irrigation canals, considering boundary conditions. It uses direct, kinematic, and convection-diffuse wave equations to depict unsteady water movement. An analytical solution for optimal water distribution using the direct wave equation is provided. Numerical solutions for kinematic and convection-diffusion equations are also offered. The article explains optimality conditions for these models, integrating mathematical frameworks with irrigation system dynamics for effective water management. These models are valuable for optimizing water distribution, ensuring efficient use in irrigation networks. By combining analytical and numerical approaches, the article enhances understanding of water flow dynamics, aiding decision-making in agricultural water management. Additionally, it sheds light on essential optimality conditions, enriching comprehension of water flow dynamics. The integration of mathematical frameworks with practical irrigation system dynamics offers valuable insights into water resource management strategies. These models are indispensable tools for optimizing water distribution, thereby enhancing the efficiency of irrigation networks. Through analytical and numerical methods, the article contributes significantly to informed decision-making in agricultural water management, facilitating sustainable practices and resource conservation. Furthermore, by elucidating the essential optimality conditions for these models, the article enhances comprehension of water flow dynamics. Integrating mathematical frameworks with practical irrigation system dynamics provides valuable insights into water resource management strategies. These models are indispensable tools for optimizing water distribution, thus improving the efficiency of irrigation networks. Through analytical and numerical methods, the article significantly contributes to informed decision-making in agricultural water management, fostering sustainable practices and resource conservation.

1. INTRODUCTION

The current theory of optimal water distribution in irrigation systems takes into account various aspects such as water efficiency, meeting the needs of different water users, and environmental constraints. However, there are additional challenges when

considering the discreteness of water supply, as it is necessary to take into account possible interruptions in the water supply and their impact on the system management processes. Dynamic programming methods, control theories, and other mathematical approaches can be used to formulate optimality conditions under such conditions[5-12]. In particular, discrete optimization methods can be used to find optimal strategies for water distribution when the resource is available [1-8]. Understanding that accounting for discreteness conditions can lead to discontinuities in both spatial and temporal parameters is key to effectively modeling and managing water flow in irrigation systems. It is important to take into account that both the parameters of the equations of motion and the functions on the right sides of these equations can be discrete in time[21-33]. When developing optimal conditions for the distribution of water among water consumers, it is necessary to take into account these features.[3-40] This may require the use of specialized optimization and control techniques that are able to take into account the discreteness over time of the system's parameters. In addition, wave phenomena that occur during the movement of flow in canals due to the discreteness of water supply should also be taken into account in the development of control models and algorithms [3-5]. This may include analyzing the characteristics of wave processes and developing control strategies aimed at minimizing their impact on the system. Comprehending the efficient allocation of water within irrigation canal networks under the discrete nature of water delivery to consumers as a problem of optimal regulation of systems with distributed parameters [6–9] represents a significant methodology that considers all aspects of the process. This method allows the formulation of an optimal control problem that integrates both the differential equations describing water flow and the discrete features of time and space, along with the wave processes that occur in the system [41–48].

METHODS AND RESULTS

For such a one-dimensional object with distributed parameters, described by one-dimensional first-order differential equations for time and second-order for a spatial variable, we can represent the equation as follows:

$$\frac{\partial Q}{\partial t} = f\left(Q, \frac{\partial Q}{\partial x}, \frac{\partial^2 Q}{\partial x^2}, u\right), \quad 0 < x < 1; 0 < t < T; \quad (1)$$

where $Q(x, t)$ is the distributed state of objects, $u(x, t)$ is distributed control, and f is a known function differentiated by a set of arguments.

The boundary conditions of the objects are written as follows:

$$\frac{\partial Q}{\partial t}(0, t) = g_1(Q(0, t), v_1(t)), \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{\partial Q}{\partial t}(1, t) = g_2(Q(1, t), v_2(t)), \quad (3)$$

where $v_1(t)$ is the boundary control action applied at $x = 0$, $v_2(t)$ is the boundary control action applied at $x = 1$; g_1, g_2 are known functions differentiated by a set of

arguments[10–15].

The initial conditions of the objects are set as follows:

$$Q(x, 0) = Q_0(x), \quad (4)$$

where $Q_0(x)$ is a known given function.

Under conditions of discreteness of water supply, the control functions are of the form:

$$u(x, t) = \sum_{i=1}^I \sum_{k=1}^K u_{ik} \delta(x - a_i) 1(t - t_k), v_1(t) = \sum_{k=1}^K v_k^1 1(t - t_{k1}), v_2(t) = \sum_{k=1}^K v_k^2 1(t - t_{k2}), \quad (5)$$

where u_{ik} , v_{1k} , and v_{2k} are the discrete values of the control actions at time t_k , t_{k1} , and t_{k2} . $\delta(x - a_i)$ is the delta Dirac function of x , and $1(t - t_{ki})$ are the unit functions of time t .

The criterion of optimal control of the object under consideration is characterized by the following quality functionality:

$$\begin{aligned} I(u(x, t), v_1(t), v_2(t), Q_0(x)) &= \int_0^{l_1} \int_0^T G\left(Q, \frac{\partial Q}{\partial x}, \frac{\partial^2 Q}{\partial x^2}, u\right) dx dt \\ &+ \int_0^{l_1} G_0(Q(x, T), Q_0(x)) dx \\ &+ \int_0^T \left[G_1(Q(0, t), v_1(t)) + G_2(Q(l, t), v_2(t)) \right] dt \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where G , G_0 , G_1 , G_2 are known functions differentiated by the set of arguments.

Control constraints are as follows:

$$u_* \leq u(x, t) \leq u^* v_{1*} \leq v_1(t) \leq v_1^* v_{2*} \leq v_2(t) \leq v_2^* Q_* \leq Q_0(x) \leq Q^* \quad (7)$$

where u^* , u_* , v_1^* , v_{1*} , v_2^* , v_{2*} , Q^* , Q_* are the specified maximum and minimum values of control functions.

Introducing a Hamiltonian with a conjugate function:

$$H = G + \lambda f. \quad (8)$$

On the basis of the methods of the calculus of variations and Lagrange factors, we obtain explicit expressions for the variation of the functional in the neighborhood of the optimal trajectory:

$$\delta I = \int_0^T \int_0^l \left(\frac{\partial H}{\partial u} \right)_0 \delta u \, dx \, dt + \quad (1)$$

$$+ \int_0^l \left[\left(\frac{\partial G_1}{\partial Q_0(x)} \right)_0 + \lambda \right] \delta Q_0(x) \, dx + \quad (2)$$

$$+ \int_0^T \left[\left(\frac{\partial H}{\partial Q'}(0, t) \right)_0 \left(\frac{\partial g_1}{\partial v_1(t)} \right)_0 \delta v_1(t) + \left(\frac{\partial H}{\partial Q'}(l, t) \right)_0 \left(\frac{\partial g_2}{\partial v_2(t)} \right)_0 \delta v_2(t) \right] dt. \quad (9)$$

In this case, the conjugate function satisfies the following differential equation:

$$\frac{\partial \lambda}{\partial t} = - \left[\left(\frac{\partial H}{\partial Q} \right)_0 - \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\frac{\partial H}{\partial Q'} \right)_0 + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} \left(\frac{\partial H}{\partial Q''} \right)_0 \right], \quad (10)$$

with boundary conditions:

$$\left(\frac{\partial G_1}{\partial Q(0, t)} \right)_0 - \left(\frac{\partial H}{\partial Q''}(0, t) \right)_0 \left(\frac{\partial g_1}{\partial Q(0, t)} \right)_0 - \left(\frac{\partial H}{\partial Q'}(0, t) \right)_0 - \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\frac{\partial H}{\partial Q''}(0, t) \right)_0 = 0, \quad (11)$$

$$\left(\frac{\partial G_2}{\partial Q(l, t)} \right)_0 - \left(\frac{\partial H}{\partial Q''}(l, t) \right)_0 \left(\frac{\partial g_2}{\partial Q(l, t)} \right)_0 - \left(\frac{\partial H}{\partial Q'}(l, t) \right)_0 - \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\frac{\partial H}{\partial Q''}(l, t) \right)_0 = 0, \quad (12)$$

conditions at a finite point in time:

$$\lambda(x, T) = \left(\frac{\partial G_0}{\partial Q(x, T)} \right)_0, \quad (13)$$

where the symbol $(\cdot)_0$ means that the corresponding quantity is computed along the optimal trajectory, $Q'_i = \partial Q_i / \partial x_i$, $Q''_i = \partial^2 Q_i / \partial x_i^2$.

In (9), the effect of the variations $\delta * u$, $\delta * v_1$, $\delta * v_2$, and $\delta * Q_0$ on the variations $\delta * I$ is clearly expressed.

Further, equating the coefficients for variations in control to zero, in the expression of the variation of the functional, we obtain the rest of the necessary conditions for the optimality of the problem under consideration.

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\frac{\partial H}{\partial u} \right)_0 &= 0, & \left(\frac{\partial G_1}{\partial Q_0(x)} + \lambda \right)_0 &= 0, \\ \left(\frac{\partial H}{\partial Q''}(0, t) \right)_0 \left(\frac{\partial g_1}{\partial v_1(t)} \right)_0 &= 0, & & \\ \left(\frac{\partial H}{\partial Q''}(l, t) \right)_0 \left(\frac{\partial g_2}{\partial v_2(t)} \right)_0 &= 0. & & \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

Thus, the necessary conditions for the optimality of the problem (1–6) are determined by the conditions given in (10–14).

Let us examine the necessary conditions for achieving optimal water distribution in irrigation canal networks under discrete water supply conditions, employing simplified models of water flow dynamics within canal segments [17–20].

3. DISCUSSION

Straight Wave Model. The objective of optimal water distribution in the straight wave model is to minimize variations in water discharge along the canal length and at its endpoint, while maintaining a discrete water supply with a specified flow rate to the respective lateral water intakes, i.e., the points of water withdrawal [17–19].

$$I = \int_0^l [Q(x, T) - Q^*]^2 dx + \int_0^T Q^2(l, t) dt, \quad (15)$$

The direct wave model has the following partial differential equation:

$$\frac{\partial Q}{\partial t} + v \frac{\partial Q}{\partial x} = q, \quad (16)$$

where $Q(x, t)$ denotes the flow rate of water along the canal length, and $q(x, t)$ represents the rate of lateral water withdrawal. In the case of discrete water supply to five concentrated intake points located at positions a_i , the expression takes the following form:

$$q(x, t) = - \sum_{i=1}^N q_i \delta(x - a_i) I(t - T). \quad (17)$$

Initial, Boundary Conditions, and Variable Definition Domains:

$$Q(x, 0) = Q_0(x), \quad Q(0, t) = u(t), \quad x \geq 0, \quad t \geq 0, \quad v > 0. \quad (18)$$

In this case, introducing the conjugate function $\lambda(x, t)$, we give expressions for the functional variation in the neighborhood of the optimal trajectory without intermediate transformations:

$$\begin{aligned} \delta I = & \int_0^l \int_0^T \left(\frac{\partial \lambda}{\partial t} - v \frac{\partial \lambda}{\partial x} \right)_0 \delta Q dx dt + \int_0^l \{ 2[Q(x, T) - Q^*] + \lambda(x, T) \}_0 \delta Q(x, T) dx + \\ & + \int_0^T [2Q(l, t) + v \lambda(l, t)]_0 \delta Q(l, t) - v \lambda(0, t)_0 \delta u(t) dt. \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

(19)

Hence, the necessary conditions for the optimality of this problem are of the form:

$$\frac{\partial \lambda}{\partial t} - v \frac{\partial \lambda}{\partial x} = 0, \lambda(x, T) = -2[Q(x, T) - Q^*], \lambda(l, t) = \frac{2}{v} Q(l, t), \quad \lambda(0, t) = 0. \quad (20)$$

The analytic solution of boundary value problems (16)-(18) and (19) on the basis of their Green's function according to [5] is written as follows:

$$Q(x, t) = \int_0^t \int_0^l G_1(x, \xi, t - \tau) w_1(\xi, \tau) d\xi d\tau, \quad (21)$$

$$\lambda(x, t) = \int_0^t \int_0^l G_2(x, \xi, t - \tau) w_2(\xi, \tau) d\xi d\tau. \quad (22)$$

where $G_1(x, \xi, t - \tau)$ and $G_2(x, \xi, t - \tau)$, $w_1(\xi, \tau)$ and $w_2(\xi, \tau)$ – Green's functions and standardizing functions, which are of the form

$$G_1(x, \xi, t - \tau) = l(x - \xi) \delta(v(t - \tau) - (x - \xi)),$$

$$G_2(x, \xi, t - \tau) = l(x - \xi) \delta(-v(t - \tau) - (x - \xi)),$$

$$w_1(x, t) = q(x, t) + Q_0(x) \delta(t) - v u(t) \delta(x),$$

$$w_2(x, t) = 2[Q(x, T) - Q^*] \delta(t - T) - 2v Q(l, t) \delta(x - l).$$

With the help of fundamental solutions of the fundamental and conjugate equations at $Q_0(x) = 0$, considering the function $u(t)$ as a step function and on the basis of the necessary conditions of optimality, the minimum of the functional is achieved by controlling

$$u_1(t) = \sum_{i=1}^N q_{N-i} l \left(t - \sum_{k=1}^i \tau_{N-k} \right), \quad (23)$$

where $\tau_i = (a_i - a_{i-1})/v$.

In this case, the solution of equation (17) will be written in analytical form

$$Q(x, t) = - \sum_{i=1}^N q_i l(x - a_i) l(v(t - T) - (x - a_i)) + l(t - vx) \sum_{i=1}^N q_{N-i} l \left(t - \sum_{k=1}^i \tau_{N-k} \right). \quad (24)$$

This approach assumes that, to control the water discharge at the lateral intake points located in various sections of the canal, it is essential to adjust the discharge at the canal's initial section in advance [14]. A graphical illustration of this concept is presented in Figure 1, shown in the lower diagram (25).

As illustrated in the figure, the control function $u(t)$ - representing the flow rate at the canal's inlet at time $t_o = T - \tau_5 - \tau_4 - \tau_3 - \tau_2 - \tau_1$ - is adjusted to match the specified discharge value of the final water intake, denoted as q_5 . Then, after the passage of time τ_5 , the control value increases by q_4 , after the time τ_4 the control increases by q_4 , after the time τ_3 the control increases by q_3 , and so on to the value q_1 , i.e. with optimal water distribution under conditions of discrete water supply in the canal, first of all, water intakes located in series from the end of the canal are provided.

Fig. 2 shows the water flow distribution function $Q(x, t)$ (24) in isometric.

Kinematic wave model. The criterion for the optimal distribution of water under the conditions of the kinematic wave model corresponds to the shape represented in equation (15). The kinematic wave model is based on the equation of conservation of mass of the flow [2,7,20].

$$\frac{\partial \omega}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial Q}{\partial x} = q, \quad Q = \omega C \sqrt{Ri}, \quad C = \frac{1}{n} R^y, \quad y = 2.5\sqrt{n} - 0.13 - 0.75\sqrt{R}(\sqrt{n} - 0.1), \quad (25)$$

where $Q(x, t)$ represents the variation in water discharge within the canal section, ω denotes the cross-sectional area of the flow, R is the hydraulic radius, C refers to the Chezy coefficient, n is the roughness coefficient, and i indicates the slope of the canal bed [23].

FIG. 1: Fig. 1: Change the water flow rate at the beginning of the canal to ensure optimal water distribution over the canal section.

Starting conditions

$$Q(x, 0) = Q_0(x), \quad \omega(x, 0) = \omega_0(x) \quad (26)$$

where $Q_0(x)$ and $\omega_0(x)$ denote the initial distributions of the flow rate and the cross-sectional area of the water flow, respectively.

The boundary conditions and the ranges of variable definitions are analogous to those in the previous problem.

Рис. 2: Fig. 2. Change the water flow rate at the beginning of the canal to ensure optimal water distribution on the canal section.

The water discharges at the intake points of the canal section, $q(x, t)$, under discrete water distribution conditions, are determined as expressed in equation (17).

Likewise, the necessary conditions of optimality are defined as

$$\frac{\partial \lambda}{\partial t} - v \frac{\partial \lambda}{\partial x} = 0, \quad \lambda(x, T) = -2[Q(x, T) - Q^*], \quad \lambda(l, t) = \frac{2}{v}Q(l, t), \quad \lambda(0, t) = 0. \quad (27)$$

where

$$v = \left(\frac{\partial Q}{\partial \omega} \right)_0.$$

In the kinematic wave model, the equations describing the main variables are nonlinear, and the equations for the conjugate variables are linear equations of the hyperbolic inverse wave type. The velocity of the reverse wave is defined as the derivative of the water flow rate over the cross-sectional area of the flow and is a variable function [41].

Convection-diffusion model. The criterion for optimal water distribution under the conditions of the convection-diffuse model is (15). The convection-diffusion model is based on the consideration of the drag force and the neglect of the inertial force [2]

$$\frac{\partial Q}{\partial t} = f \left(Q, \frac{\partial Q}{\partial x}, \frac{\partial^2 Q}{\partial x^2}, q \right) \quad (28)$$

where $f = - \left(\frac{\partial Q}{\partial K} \frac{\partial K}{\partial h} \right) \frac{\partial Q}{\partial x} + \frac{K^2}{2B|Q|} \frac{\partial^2 Q}{\partial x^2} + q$, K is the flow modulus, B is the top flow width.

The flow modulus K characterizes the magnitude of the frictional forces and is determined by the following formula:

$$K = \omega \cdot C \sqrt{R}. \quad (30)$$

The rest of the parameters, the initial and boundary conditions, as well as the domains

of variable definition, have the same appearance as in the kinematic wave model.

On the basis of the above methodology, the necessary conditions for optimality in the case of the convection-diffuse model are determined

$$\frac{\partial \lambda}{\partial t} - v_1 \frac{\partial \lambda}{\partial x} - v_2 \frac{\partial^2 \lambda}{\partial x^2} = 0, \quad (31)$$

where

$$v_1 = \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial Q'} \right)_0 = \left(\frac{\partial Q}{\partial K} \frac{\partial K}{\partial h} \right)_0, \quad v_2 = \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial Q''} \right)_0 = \left(\frac{K^2}{2B|Q|} \right)_0. \quad (32)$$

Boundary conditions

$$v_2 \frac{\partial \lambda}{\partial x}(0, t) = (v_2 - v_1)\lambda(0, t), \quad v_2 \frac{\partial \lambda}{\partial x}(l, t) = (v_1 - v_2)\lambda(l, t), \quad (33)$$

conditions by the end of the process $\lambda(x, T) = -2[Q(x, T) - Q^*]$.

In the convection-diffusion model, equation (29) for the principal variable is nonlinear, and equation (31) for the conjugate variables is a linear parabolic equation with a convective term. The coefficients in these equations are defined as derivatives of the functions on the right-hand side of equation (32) for the variables Q' and Q'' respectively. Boundary conditions are expressed as conditions of the third kind.

For both models, kinematic and convective-diffusion waves, the optimal control can be determined using numerical methods for modeling the movement of water in channels and the necessary optimality conditions for an approximate solution of the problems of optimal water distribution under conditions of discreteness of water supply.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The article presents the development of mathematical models and the necessary optimality conditions for solving the problem of optimal water resource distribution in the main canals of irrigation systems, taking into account the boundary conditions. As a mathematical representation of the unsteady water flow within the canal sections, simplified models—such as the equations of linear (straight) waves, kinematic waves, and convection–diffusion waves—were employed. An analytical solution to the optimal water distribution problem in main canals, irrigation systems, and related facilities was derived using the straight wave equation. Additionally, numerical solutions for specific cases based on the kinematic and convection–diffusion models of unsteady water flow in irrigation system components were obtained, and the corresponding optimality conditions for these models were established.

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